

THE RULES OF WRITING SCIENTIFIC ARTICLES

Turkan Ismailli

Azerbaijan, Nakhchivan State University

Abstract

The article deals with the rules and processes of writing scientific articles. The article explains how to choose titles, how to write a detailed summary, what to emphasize in the introduction and the main part. At the same time, discussion and method preparation, references and conclusion section, which are required in high-index journals, are mentioned. In addition, the ethical rules of writing articles are also touched upon.

Keywords: scientific articles, ethical rules, structure of articles, plagiarism

Introduction. Scientific articles are written to share a scientific discovery or research with the society. The most important characteristics of a scientific article are clarity and precision. These texts are written in a short, concise and immediately understandable manner by people who have the necessary equipment in their fields. In scientific articles, previous studies on the subject under investigation are used. It is a requirement of scientific ethics to indicate the name of the person who has previously worked on this subject and the name of his work.

Sections of Scientific Articles. The title is very important detail in scientific articles. The title of the text should consist of at least a few words that can convey the content. A scientific text without an appropriate title cannot attract the attention of the reader. Because a good title is the sign of the successful text. Most people will read the title of the article first. He or she can decide whether to read it or not based on the impression he gets from the title. The words in the title should be chosen well and be related to each other. Title length should be adjusted well. Word order in titles should be taken into consideration. Because most of the grammatical errors made in titles occur during word order. It is important to remember that the title is an etiquette of the article. Sentences are not formed by subject, object and verb arrangement. It should be simpler and attention should be paid to the order of the words.

Preparing a short summary: It is defined as a reduced version of the article. It should contain a summary of the main parts of the article. It should indicate what is covered in the article and should not exceed 250 words. In the brief summary, the purpose of the research, the methodology used should be described, the findings should be summarized and finally a general conclusion should be given. The short summary should lead to the need to read the entire scientific article. Unnecessary details about the subject should not be included in this area. In the summary sections of scientific articles, there is a reduced form of what is explained in the entire text into a paragraph. The summary should be able to fully express the content of the text. Additionally, the summary section focuses on the aims of the research, research methods, research findings, results and the importance of these results. Summary and abstract sections should give brief summary information about the study. The length of the abstract section should not exceed 200 words, but should not be

less than 100 words. Things to consider in the main text can be listed as follows;

Writing Introduction: It refers to the first part of a text. It comes after the title and brief summary. Present tense should be used when writing the introduction. Its most important purpose is to briefly state why you wrote the article. This is a section that provides information about what the problem is and its scope [4]. Information should be given about which method was used in the research. The main findings of the research should be written down. The main conclusions should be stated along with the findings. Some authors do not mention their most important discoveries in the article introduction. This is not found true by scientists. It is generally accepted that these rules are included in the introduction section.

Main part. The purpose of body text is to provide the reader with the information they need in a clear and easy-to-read format. To give the article a clear structure, it is important to organize it into paragraphs. Each paragraph should be centered around a main point or idea. The main idea of the article is usually introduced in a topic sentence. The topic sentence should generally build on the previous paragraph and reveal the point intended to be made in this paragraph. Transition words can be used to create clear connections between sentences. After the topic sentence, evidence should be provided, such as data, examples, or quotes from relevant sources. Basic information should be given to enable easy and accurate understanding of what is stated in the article. The meaning of any terms and abbreviations used in the article should be explained. The necessity of the study is revealed. It is explained how the subject covered in the article was handled in previous publications [3]. What method was followed in the research that is the subject of the article and the reason why this method was chosen is revealed. The main findings of the research are expressed and the results are stated. In the materials and methods section of scientific articles, the author must explain to the reader why and how it is used. In this way, the author ensures that another expert repeats the same study after him.

Writing the Method Section. In the method section, it is required to explain it by including all the details. It should contain information about how the research was conducted.

Writing Conclusions. Writing conclusions is perhaps the most important part of the scientific article. When writing the conclusion, present tense should be

used. When stating the results, they should be written short, clear and simple. Instead of using repetitive data in the conclusion section, sample data should be used [2]. A general description of the experiment performed should be given in the scientific article. Details about the experiment should not be included. The introduction and method section are designed to state why and how the results were obtained.

Writing Discussion: This is the last part and is more difficult to write than other parts. Any findings that are not included in the results should not be included. What was stated earlier in the article should not be repeated in this section. A comparison of the literature should be made, and only those that support the conclusion should not be used when making a comparison. It should be noted that the results are in agreement or contrast with previously published publications. The conclusions reached should be stated quite clearly [1]. Past tense and present tense are used in the discussion. Present tense should be used when describing the work of others, and past tense should be used when talking about the study results. One of the things that should be taken into consideration regarding academic writing techniques is that the subject headings should be compatible with the content of the subject and ensure integrity in this context. The title and content should not be unrelated to each other, and the subject mentioned in the title must be explained in the text.

Scientists are not evaluated by their talent, intelligence and likeability, but also by their publications and enter the scientific arena. Scientific articles are studies conducted in accordance with scientific principles and ethical rules and written and published in scientific forms.

Bibliography Preparation. Preparing a bibliography is a very important issue in terms of scientific ethics. When citing sources in academic articles, the rules of APA (American Psychological Association) are used. APA was created by the American Psychological Association. Bibliography is an important element in academic writings and publications and is the section at the end of the text where the sources used are listed according to a certain system. Resources in this section; The work can be single-authored, double-authored, multi-authored, thesis, article, etc.

Academic language and style is a style that should be preferred in scientific / academic research. In academic language and writings, the writer should avoid personal and emotional expressions, polemics and daily conversational language and expression within the framework of this style. Generalizing and vague expressions and thoughts that cannot be proven should not be included. The most important feature of academic language and style and academic writings is the method defined as "word economy", which means expressing what is intended to be explained in the clearest way and with the fewest words. Another feature of academic language and writings is that they are written using the terms and concepts of the relevant scientific field.

In academic legal writing, everyone should be aware that they must comply with academic ethical

standards. One of these ethical considerations is not to allow plagiarism.

Plagiarism – full or partial disclosure of the work under the name of another person, that is, publishing the literary, literary, literary or other works of the original under his own name, or concealing the authorship of the original. The creation of a new work by smuggling the work or a share of it without showing its origin or author.

Verbal plagiarism – in this form, those who are engaged in research usually record in their articles any text that is specific to others. The most widely spread types being copy and paste and shake and paste.

Masked or suppressed plagiarism: at this time it is relatively difficult to determine whether an academic writer allows plagiarism in his writing, because he changes the text or idea he is plagiarizing and does. The most commonly used types are paraphrasing, technical suppression, translated plagiarism.

Structure and idea plagiarism: the person who gives rise to plagiarism simply records someone else's idea in his writing and does not refer to it, in a way, he appears as the author of the whole idea.

Falsification: Deliberately changing data and/or results and/or omitting data.

Duplication: Publishing the same work in more than one publication medium *Slicing:* To publish a work by dividing it in order to increase the number of publications.

Piracy: Unlike plagiarism, unauthorized copies of a work are made reproduction and commercial sale by individuals.

Conclusion

The article explains the structural and ethical rules that should be followed when writing scientific articles. It is emphasized that it is very important to write an interesting title for the article and a summary that expresses the article briefly and concretely. Because if the summary is interesting, the reader will continue reading it. It is noted that when writing the main part, it is also important to divide it into paragraphs. In the final part, the results obtained from the article should be concretely and clearly reflected. Following the ethical rules during the writing of the article will also increase the authority of the scientist.

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